

Kinetic Adhesion Test to determine Adhesive Energy

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Abstract

Understanding of the flow characteristic in the pneumatic conveying is imperative to operate and design Direct Metal Additive Manufacturing (DMAM) systems, and the ability to analyze the process in detail is key to the increase of its capabilities and sustainability. Very clean and unoxidized metallic powders can have a strong surface affinity, resulting in a strong cohesion propensity. Simulations need to take this effect into account, and one of the most accepted ways to represent the interaction is the Johnson-Kendall-Roberts (JKR) contact model. This work presents an open-source device and the relative procedure to determine the Adhesive Energy of the material. Measurements realized using the presented device are more inexpensive and less time consuming than other techniques like AFM, acting on a large sample, but without mediating through the bulk flows (rheometer). The obtained Adhesive Energy parameter is directly related to the contact model it will be used with.

Introduction

Transport of fine powders is one bottleneck of many industrial processes, ranging from food processing, mining, pharmaceutical, powder metallurgy, and many other. Delivery of the powder from storage to the active part of the process is often done by means of pneumatic conveying, which is greatly hindered by powder cohesion. For some processes, like Laser Metal Deposition, it can be difficult to devise an alternative means of delivery, therefore understanding the effect of particle adhesion is crucial to its advancement [1].

On the micro-scale, adhesion between fine particles and particle-surface is determined by a variety of interactions: Van der Waals (dispersion, dipole-induced-dipole, charge-fluctuation...), Electrostatic (Coulomb, ionic, dipolar, hydrogen bonding...)[2]. Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) is able to directly measure a single particle's interaction. Other methods are based on centrifugation, vibration, fluid-dynamic interaction, impact [3]. On the other end of the spectrum, bulk characterization is performed on a large sample, determining the average behavior of the material. Several commercial tools are available to empirically calibrate numerical simulations, spanning from quasi-static to dynamic behavior.

The proposed method falls in the impact methods category, which has the advantage of being a meso-scale type approach. It lays its foundation in the widely accepted Johnson-Kendall-Roberts (JKR) contact model [4], which treats the adhesive interface essentially as a brittle crack, following Griffith's considerations in the definition of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) [5].

Basic principle

In the test, particles are first dispersed onto a substrate, where the surface preparation can correspond to the expected operating conditions. The initial Particle Size Distribution (PSD) is determined via an optical method.

The device is used to conduct the test, ensuring repeatability. At its core, a heavy steel anvil is suspended on springs, which decouple it from the rest of the structure. The sample is contained in a carrier, which is also made out of steel. The objective is to impact two hard surfaces, detaching the particles in a sharp impact, or an impulsive load. From in the freefall condition, both the particles and substrate accelerate to v_i , the velocity at which the impact happens. Falling, the particles attached to the substrate acquire kinetic energy according to the formula $E_k = \frac{1}{2}mv_i^2$. The energy is then balanced with the adhesive energy of the contact, which directly determines whether the particle will detach or not. Usually, larger particles detach at a lower velocity than smaller ones, therefore resulting in a different PSD, represented in Figure 1. If the particles are perfectly spherical and both surfaces in contact are perfectly uniform, the critical radius R_c is clearly defined as half the diameter of the largest particle still attached to the surface after the impact.

The Dupre work of adhesion between two dissimilar surfaces is $\Gamma = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12}$, where γ_1 and γ_2 are the intrinsic surface energies of the solids, and γ_{12} of the interface. The bonding energy of the contact is equal to the contact energy over the contact area A , of radius a if circular. The bonding energy then becomes $U_S = -\pi a^2 \Gamma$ for a sphere on a plane. The contact radius determined by the balance between surface (U_S), elastic (U_E) and potential energy from the applied load (U_P) is the base to derive the JKR contact model [4].

Hardware description

The steel anvil stands at the bottom of an aluminum structure, decoupled by a set of springs. The sample carrier is a steel housing which will impact the anvil. A mobile arm holds the magnet which will be used to release the sample carrier. The falling velocity is measured by a photoelectric switch connected to the central microcontroller. The device can be equipped with a sensing cable to measure the contact time between the sample carrier and the anvil, allowing to reproduce the procedure by Zafar et.al. [8]. The design files are released in a public repository [9] and the instructions are published in [10], allowing it to be freely reproduced and improved upon.

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